

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NABITAKA****FIRST NAME: LINDA****PROGRAM CODE: DARM****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar("EUCLID University Detailed Syllabus (ELEMENTS) for ACA-401D: International Academic Writing (Doctorate) | Euclid University" n.d.)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15)
2. American Vs British (EUCLID 2021, 24)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33)
4. Writing style (EUCLID 2021, 40)
5. CMS sheet (EUCLID 2021, 43)
6. Latin abbreviations and expressions (EUCLID 2021, 58)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC AND PROFESSIONAL WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The first step for any new undertaking is usually the hardest step, this has not been any different for me on this journey of doctoral studies. It was with a lot of apprehension and trepidation that I finally enrolled into a doctoral study program after many trials and failures. Even after the enrolment, understanding the requirements for getting off the ground has been a challenge. After a lot of procrastination, I was finally able to log into the EUCLID system and download the start-up pack for the first course.

As the entry course to doctoral studies, I was not sure what to expect from the first course period. I was very surprised to learn that it was almost a re-introduction to English grammar and punctuation something I thought I was very conversant with. It has been an eye-opener to know that most of the writing I have done up to date has probably not been well thought out in a number of areas including grammar, punctuation and style. With an open mind, I look forward to this journey of improving my writing and becoming efficient

at academic and professional writing. The next few weeks will certainly prove to be exciting and will go a long way to show that learning indeed never ends!

2) ESSAY WRITING

There are many types of essays, however, this paper will discuss essays intended for academic purposes (EUCLID 2021, 7). Almost all academic writing shares formal prose register, citations, and references to other work (EUCLID 2021, 7).

The first thing I have learned about academic essay writing is that one should not procrastinate but start as early as possible. To write a good paper, one needs to read and research the topic extensively and think before getting down to write. It is important to define the topic you are writing about then analyze and draft a plan.

In researching the topic, it is important to ask yourself what you already know about the topic, what you need to know, how the material will help your writing, and if it can support your answer. While reading it is also important to write down notes that will form the basis of the essay.

The essay constitutes three parts:

- Introduction: in which one opens with an orientation, then answers the question with a thesis statement and provides a summary of the essay
- Body: in which you answer the question through discussion and develop argument using examples
- Conclusion: in which you re-state the answer and summarize the main points.

Some key issues one needs to take note of when writing include stating the main thesis at the beginning, stay focused, avoid generalities, and write clearly. The writing should not boring, and any assertions made should be supported. Additionally, the views taken should be seriously discussed and plagiarism should be avoided (EUCLID 2021, 13-14).

Finally, one has to reference the essay and edit it before handing in.

a) Punctuations

The general rule of punctuations is to use as little as is necessary without changing the meaning of the sentence (EUCLID 2021, 16). Punctuations marks such as commas, quotation marks, ellipses, brackets, quotation marks, full stops colon and semi colon, to name but a few, maybe used in writing depending on need. For example; apostrophes are used where there are omitted letter, or when using compound and plural nouns; brackets

are used in place of dashes or commas or when one is giving extra information; commas are used to surround a non-defining clause which adds descriptive information but can be removed without losing the meaning; colons may be used to introduce sub-clauses that are part of a preceding statement but does not introduce a new concept while semicolon is used to link two related parts of a sentence.

One needs to be very careful to always use the correct punctuations in the right places so as not to distort the meaning of a sentence and for correct writing.

b) American Vs British

Although both are variants of World English (EUCLID 2021, 25) there are some notable differences between American and British English in terms of pronunciation, spelling, grammar, and syntax. American English has grown in popularity since the end of the World War II. This is attributed to the growing American population which is far greater than the native English population “SAE/SBE ca 70% vs. 17% of all native English” (EUCLID 2021, 25), the magnitude of their higher education, as well as publishing industry, mass media, technological influence, and appeal of American culture.

Other differences are attributed to their differing national histories, cultural development, as well as what is considered politically correct, and ethnic diversity. Also very important is the difference in the use of punctuation marks such as commas, periods, quotation marks, writing of dates, and informal Vs formal letter writing.

c) Plagiarism

Plagiarism in academic writing is an offense with serious consequences (EUCLID 2021, 34). Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information for example through copying, paraphrasing, or quoting. All effort must be taken to avoid plagiarism. This can be done by.

- Citing/indicating the source of information; this could be in-text citing where the source is included within the text as you write with both author’s name and the page where the information was got
- Quotations: in which the author’s same words are used as they are in the original text. Quotations may be short or long. When long quotations are used, they should be indented as separate paragraphs while short quotations are put in quotation marks
- Paraphrasing: in which the writer uses the original author’s ideas and information but writes it in their own way. When paraphrasing one has to ensure that: the writer uses their own words, expresses the original writer’s ideas while using a different writing style from what the original author used, provides an accurate representation of the original author and still cites the original source of information.

Sometimes, however, it may not be necessary to cite everything especially when the information used is common knowledge or has been repeated in many different sources.

Other key details include putting a list of citations/references at the end of the paper/book, following a particular format when noting citations that are different for books and online materials, and having a logical flow.

d) Writing Style

The writing style refers to a consistent approach to elements of writing. Different writers and institutions subscribe to different styles for example Euclid University recommends Chicago Rules (Turabian) writing using American English (EUCLID 2021, 41).

Many writers do not feel a need for a particular writing style but rather that Standard English writing style is innate in all writers. However, having a particular way of documenting rules or features allows for consistency. Writing styles are associated with certain types of writing such as technical, commercial, business, and journalism, and this, therefore, allows for consistency. Writers tend to develop writing styles depending on customers or projects and in keeping with previous styles used. And this is of even more importance for freelance writers.

Due to the fact that there are no single authoritative English writing styles, there is always a certain amount of debate on elements of style (EUCLID 2021, 41) Styles can differ in several elements including length of sentences, layout, fonts used, depth of subject, structure, paragraph, and use of symbols, headings and lists among others. References of writing styles can be found in n Strunk's, 'The Elements of Style,' The Economist style guide, The Chicago Manual of Style, and the BBC news style guide for news and current affairs.

e) CMS crib sheet

Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996; published by the University of Chicago Press (EUCLID 2021, 44). Some of the specifications of Chicago style include:

- Spelling; recommend Webster's Third International and Merriam-Webster's Collegiate Dictionaries
- Abbreviations are rarely used; sentences begin with upper case, acronyms must be introduced and should avoid starting sentences with acronyms; names of countries, states or provinces have to be spelled out

- Capitalization: In major headings, the first character in each word is capitalized. Book, articles, ethnic/racial groups, and geographical places are all capitalized
- Compound words: These are words that work together in a specified order and cannot be reversed or re-arranged. These should be hyphenated; however, common prefixes do not need hyphenating.
- Italics and quotations: These are used to highlight words, indicate irony, or translate words in a different language. Keywords, titles of books foreign terms can be put in italics or quotations marks for emphasis
- Citations are placed in quotation marks or indented
- Numbers: round numbers are written out, same for numbers beginning a sentence and ordinal numbers. Numbers and symbols should not be mixed as well as numbers and numerals, however, one can mix two sets of numbers if they are embedded in a single sentence. Compound numbers can be hyphenated.
- Other important issues to take note of in Chicago style include page formats, justification, margins, spacing, headings, footnotes, endnotes, and bibliographies.

f) Latin abbreviations and expressions

Latin abbreviations and expressions can be used for footnotes, bibliographies, and informal writing. However, in business and technical writing, the English equivalent of the Latin abbreviation should be used to avoid misinterpretations (EUCLID 2021, 59)

3) CONCLUSION

In conclusion, as the opening course for doctorate studies, ACA-401D period 1 has been good inception into writing and publishing. To become more efficient at academic writing, I will need to keep referring to the ACA-401D period course pack until I have learned all the basics of international and academic writing.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.